

Chemical Examination of the Fixed Oil from the Seeds of *Celastrus Paniculatus* Willd.

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Celastrus Paniculatus, a shrub of the natural order *Celastrineae*, is found in Bihar, Bengal, Burma and Ceylon (Kanny Lall Dey, "The Indigenous Drugs of India," 1896, p. 74; Nadkarni, "The Indian Materia Medica" 1927, p. 187). Its seeds yield an oil "said to be a sovereign remedy in beri-beri, and a stimulant." In Ayurvedic and Unani Medicines use of the seeds and of the oil is recommended in rheumatism, gout, paralysis and leprosy (*cf.* Nadkarni, *loc. cit.*; Chopra, "The Indigenous Drugs of India," 1933, p. 473.). The oil is reputed to be a nerve-stimulant and a brain-tonic. Since very little work has been done on the oil, the following investigation was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL.

50 G. of the crushed seeds were extracted with the following solvents successively in a soxhlet:

	Extract.
Petroleum ether (b. p. 50—60°)	52.2 %
Ethyl ether	1.6
Chloroform	0.5
Ethyl acetate	0.4
Alcohol	2.8
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	57.5
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The petroleum ether extract gave a thick brownish yellow oil with an unpleasant taste. The other extracts consisted of highly coloured viscous materials about which no definite conclusions could be drawn.

Though the occurrence of an alkaloid in the seeds is mentioned in the literature (Wehmer, "Die pflanzenstoffe," 1931, p. 717; Chopra, *loc. cit.*), no satisfactory evidence for it was obtained when the seeds were tested with Prollius fluid. 300 G. of the seeds were subjected to steam distillation, and the steam-volatile matter was found to be 0.015%. This material was a dark brown solid with a strong odour

resembling that of the oil-cake. The aqueous extracts of the seeds contained traces of tannins and of reducing sugars, but no starch. The amount of reducing sugars did not increase on acid hydrolysis.

Fatty Oil.

The fatty oil was extracted by petroleum ether (b. p. 50—60°) and the purified material had the following constants.

Specific gravity 25°/25°	0.9586
Refractive index at 30°	1.4747
Saponification value	239.2
Acid value	44.4
Iodine value (Hanus).	102.9
Reichert-Meissl value	62.8
Acetyl value	130.1
Unsaponifiable matter	5.7%
Hehner value	75.2%

Mixed Fatty Acids.

2 Kg. of the oil were saponified, and the acids that were liberated, were reconverted into sodium soap. This, in the form of dry shavings, was extracted with ether in a soxhlet to obtain the unsaponifiable matter. The fatty acids were next set free, and a purified sample was found to have the following constants.

Mean mol. wt. of the mixed fatty acids	275.3
Iodine value " " (Hanus)	112.6
Solid or saturated acids (Twitchell's method)	30.54%
Liquid or unsaturated acids ...	68.48%

The mixed fatty acids were resolved into their saturated and unsaturated components by Twitchell's lead salt method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, **13**, 806). During the process a small amount of a brown resinous substance separated out. The saturated and the unsaturated acids obtained had the following constants.

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	Mean mol. wt.	Iodine value (Hanus.).
Solid acids	264.0	1.8
Liquid acids	335.7	154.9

Liquid Fatty Acids.

The liquid acid mixture was esterified with methyl alcohol, and the ester (283 g.) was distilled at 1 mm. pressure. The bulk of the distillate (240 g.) passed over between 170°—180° and had mean mol. weight 277.7 and iodine value 166.2.

A portion of the acid (4 g.) obtained by saponification was treated with bromine according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils and Fats," 1913, Vol. I, p. 573). 1.7 G. of a dull white ether-insoluble bromo compound separated. This material dissolved completely in benzene and on purification gave hexabromostearic acid (m. p. 181.5; M.W., 757), indicating the presence of linolenic acid. From the filtrate no tetrabromostearic acid could be isolated.

Another portion of the liquid acid mixture (15 g.) was oxidised by cold dilute alkaline permanganate. From the mixture of hydroxy acids so formed the following were isolated.

Acids.	M. p.	M. W. (found.)	M. W. calculated.
Dihydroxystearic	131°	316.2	316.4
Tetrahydroxystearic	(a) 154°—155°	347.2	
	(b) 167°—168°	346.2	348.4
	(c) 171°	351	
Hexahydroxystearic	(a) 166°	376.9	
	(b) 194°	379.8	380.4

Thus the occurrence of oleic, linoleic and linolenic acids among the unsaturated acids is established.

Solid Fatty Acids.

The solid acid mixture, obtained above, was slightly coloured. It was esterified with methyl alcohol. 394 G. of the mixed esters were distilled under a pressure of 1 mm.

The major portion of the distillate A (319 g.) came over at 153°-158°. The rest B (67 g.) was collected at 158-165°. The residue in the flask including loss amounted to 8 g. A consisted entirely of methyl palmitate (M.W. of acid from saponification value, 258.7). From this palmitic acid (m.p. 61.5-62°; M.W., 258.4) was obtained in quantitative yield. The acid from the residues after careful purification and recrystallisations from ethyl acetate melted at 78° (M.W. 393), and it did not depress the melting point of pure cerotic acid (m.p. 78°; M.W. 396.).

Fraction B was again subjected to careful refractionation at a pressure less than 1 mm.

Fraction.	Temp. range.	Weight.	M. W. of acid from the saponification value.
I	158-162°	29 g.	264.6
II	162-170°	16	270.4
III	170-178°	11.5	276.8
IV	178°	3.5	278.9
V	Residue including loss.	7	—

Fraction I.—This gave an acid which corresponded to an eutectic mixture of palmitic and stearic acids. Repeated crystallisations from various solvents gave a product melting at 56-57° (M.W. 268).

Fractions II and III.—The crude acids from these after repeated crystallisations from alcohol yielded pure stearic acid (m.p. 69.5-70°; M.W., 284.3). Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester melted at 97.5°.

Fraction IV.—The acid liberated from this fraction, after a few crystallisations, melted at 62° (M.W., 296), and could not be examined further.

Fraction V.—This was saponified, and the acid liberated after repeated crystallisations from ethyl acetate melted at 76° and had M.W. 370.6. Its *p*-phenylphenacyl ester melted at 100°. It is, therefore, to be regarded as crude lignoceric acid.

Volatile Acids.

Since the Reichert-Meissl value for the oil was found to be unusually high, the nature of the volatile acids present was examined.

250 G. of the oil were saponified with alcoholic potash and the

alcohol was distilled over. The aqueous solution of the soap was acidified with sulphuric acid and the resulting mixture was subjected to steam distillation till the distillate contained hardly any trace of acid. The distillate was neutralised with potassium hydroxide and evaporated to a small volume. On acidifying this with sulphuric acid and cooling a mass of brownish flakes appeared. This was separated, dissolved in alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. The crystalline material, that separated out, was recrystallised from boiling water, when it was obtained in colourless glistening plates, m.p. 121° (M.W. 122), and it was found to be benzoic acid (m.p. of *p*-phenylphenacyl ester, $167-68^{\circ}$).

After the separation of benzoic acid, the aqueous solution was treated with some more sulphuric acid and again subjected to steam distillation. The distillate was neutralised with litharge and the solution was evaporated to dryness. The lead salt thus obtained was dried at 120° and decomposed at 150° by dry hydrogen sulphide. A colourless liquid was collected and this was freed from dissolved hydrogen sulphide by distilling it repeatedly over some more of the lead salt. The distillate (b.p. $100-120^{\circ}$), thus obtained, had the characteristic odour of acetic acid and it had no reducing properties. The silver salt was prepared and from this the silver content was found to be 64.59% corresponding exactly to that of silver acetate.

The bulk of the liquid was carefully fractionated and the fraction boiling at 113.5° had the equivalent weight 60.64 and consisted of pure acetic acid (m.p. of the *p*-toluidide, 146° ; m.p. of the *p*-phenylphenacyl ester, 111° .)

Thus the volatile acids were found to consist principally of acetic acid together with a small quantity of benzoic acid.

Unsaponifiable Matter.

From the unsaponifiable matter only a small quantity of a phyto-sterol (m.p. 136°) could be isolated. Its acetate melted at 119° . The main bulk of the unsaponifiable matter, after a number of crystallisations from acetone gave a white granular non-nitrogenous material melting at $61-61.5^{\circ}$. This was neutral in character and did not give any tests for the presence of either hydroxyl or carbonyl groups. Considerable difficulty was felt in obtaining concordant combustion values. On keeping it for several days it gradually resinified.